

The results of p_n determinations for mixtures of two sets of equimolar parent solutions of nickel nitrate and acetic acid, one having concentration $C=0.2$ and another set $C=0.1$, have been shown in Table I. The values of 'Y' against the corresponding values of 'x' from Table I, for mixtures of nickel nitrate and acetic acid solutions, both being at concentration $C=0.2M$, have been graphically represented by curve I, and those for both parent solutions at concentration $C=0.1M$, by curve II, in Fig. 1.

FIG. 2

(The sign $\square$ represents the plot of pK_2/μ from Table II of part IX).

The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures, studied in the present work, have been obtained by following the same procedure as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and these are shown in Table II. As in the previous case (vide Part I), the plot of ' K ' against ' μ ' from Table II yields a smooth curve, which has not been used to evaluate the value of ' K ' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. In Fig. 2, the graph $pK (= -\log K)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table II gives a straight line curve which on extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ gives the value of pK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant, K . These values of ' pK ' and ' K ' at $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ are 1.12 and 75.9×10^{-3} at $21.3-22^\circ$ respectively.

Critical comments on the previous work on the subject, as also on the present work have been made in Part IX of this series.

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SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART IX. NICKEL ACETATO COMPLEXES

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p_n values of aqueous solution mixtures of nickel acetate and nitric acid at different concentrations, after attainment of equilibrium, have been determined and the data obtained have been utilised to calculate the mass action constants, K_1 and K_2 , for the two successive equilibria, $NiAc_2 \rightleftharpoons NiAc^+ + Ac^-$ and $NiAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Ni^{2+} + Ac^-$, by applying Bjerrum's method. The inapplicability of the method of Siddhanta and Banerjee (Part III) has been accounted for and a method has been suggested to calculate the values of thermodynamic dissociation constants, K_1 and K_2 , in a similar way as described in Part VII of the series.

Nickel acetate dissociates in aqueous solution in two stages :

In this paper the thermodynamic dissociation constants, ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' (equations 1 and 2) have been determined from a measurement of p_H of solution mixtures of nickel acetate and nitric acid by adopting exactly the same procedure as followed in the case of manganese acetate (Part VII, *issue*, p. 419).

$$K_1 = \frac{c_{\text{NiAc}^+} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{NiAc}_2}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{NiAc}^+} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{NiAc}_2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

and

$$K_2 = \frac{c_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{NiAc}^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{NiAc}^+}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The procedure employed in the case of lead acetate (Part III, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 323) could not be adopted here for exactly the same reasons as described in the case of manganese acetate (Part VII, *loc. cit.*). By averaging all the values of ' K_1 ' obtained in Table II, we get $K_1 = 2.06 \times 10^{-1}$ at room temperature. As in the case of manganese acetate (Part VII, *loc. cit.*), the value of ' K_1 ', obtained here, is not at all accurate and is only indicative of the order. The value of ' K_2 ', however, is fairly accurate, as it has been found out by graphical extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$. The $pK_2/\sqrt{\mu}$ plot from the data in this paper has been shown by $\square$ mark in the $pK/\sqrt{\mu}$ plot for nickel nitrate and acetic acid mixtures, represented in Fig. 2 in Part VIII (this *issue*, p. 423). It will be seen that all these points fall on the same straight line as that representing $pK/\sqrt{\mu}$ obtained from the data for nickel nitrate and acetic acid mixtures (Part VIII, *loc. cit.*). The value of the thermodynamic constant ' K_2 ' is therefore same as that obtained in Part VIII, and it is $K_2 = 75.9 \times 10^{-3}$ at room temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel acetate (Fine chemical, Hopkins, and Williams Ltd., London) was purified by crystallising from acetic acid. The residue was then washed with ice-cold water and finally with ether. [Calc. for $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ni, 23.60%. Found: Ni, 23.40%].

Stock solutions of nickel acetate and nitric acid were prepared in which nickel was estimated with dimethylglyoxime and the strength of the acid by standard alkali titration. In the preparation of solution mixtures such calculated volumes of stock solutions were taken from a microburette that on diluting the mixture to 10 c.c., the desired initial concentrations, C and C_0 , for nickel acetate and nitric acid respectively, were obtained. After keeping the mixtures in a closed room for about 4 hours to reach equilibrium, the p_H values were determined by following the same procedure and observing the same precautions as described in Part II (*ibid*, 1958, 35, 279) of this work.

TABLE I

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part III (*loc. cit.*) of this work.

Soln. No.	C^*	C_A^*	t°	ρ_H	$\frac{a_A \cdot \times 10^3}{(K_A = 1.80 \times 10^{-5})}$	$a_A \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$	$a_A^{-3} \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$
1	0.045	0.050	32.8	4.398	22.51	-35.40	2.10
2	0.060	"	32.5	4.646	39.85	-39.42	4.73
3	0.075	"	32.8	4.764	52.26	-29.84	5.85
4	0.090	"	32.5	4.882	68.60	-31.95	9.09
5	0.105	"	32.6	4.940	78.40	-22.47	9.66
6	0.120	"	32.5	5.003	90.60	-18.77	11.61
7	0.135	"	32.8	5.05	101.01	-13.59	12.94
8	0.150	"	32.5	5.09	110.70	- 8.50	14.13
9	0.165	"	32.8	5.12	118.58	- 2.62	14.63
10	0.180	"	32.5	5.17	133.10	- 2.33	18.33
11	0.195	"	32.8	5.20	142.63	+ 1.71	19.85
12	0.210	"	32.5	5.23	152.80	+ 5.06	21.80
13	0.225	"	32.8	5.23	152.80	+13.72	19.15
14	0.240	"	32.5	5.27	167.55	+14.33	23.27
15	0.300	"	33.5	5.35	201.30	+28.11	29.20
16	0.360	"	"	5.40	226.10	+42.73	31.79
17	0.420	"	"	5.44	247.90	+55.83	33.77
18	0.480	"	"	5.49	277.75	+66.88	39.99
19	0.180	0.036	33.0	5.40	135.67	+10.01	15.68
20	"	0.045	"	5.20	128.34	+ 4.57	15.29
21	"	0.060	"	5.03	115.74	+ 2.67	12.77
22	"	0.075	"	4.921	112.58	- 4.94	13.78
23	"	0.090	"	4.817	106.29	-10.57	13.54
24	"	0.100	32.3	4.762	104.04	-16.03	14.16
25	"	0.105	33.0	4.727	100.80	-16.86	13.56
26	"	0.1125	32.3	4.691	99.41	-21.42	14.14
27	"	0.125	"	4.599	89.35	-21.07	11.74
28	"	0.1375	"	4.539	85.61	-26.96	11.94
29	"	0.150	"	4.468	79.50	-30.15	11.11
30	"	0.1625	"	4.386	71.14	-30.19	9.30
31	"	0.175	"	4.325	66.55	-34.58	9.03

* C and C_A denote respectively the molar conc. of $NiAc_2$ and HNO_3 .

TABLE II

Soln. No. (as per Table I).	$^{**}CNiA_0^+ \times 10^3$.	$^{**}CNi^{2+} \times 10^3$.	$CNiA_0 \times 10^3$ (Part. VII, Eq. 5).	μ (Part III, Eq. 10).	$CA_0^- \times 10^3$ (Pt. III, Eq. 8b) $K_0 = 1.75 \times 10^{-5}$.	$K_1 \times 10^{+1}$ (Eq. 1).	$K_2 \times 10^3$ (Eq. 2).
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
1	13.32	29.59	2.09	0.10209	31.82	0.957†	1.575
2	25.60	32.12	2.28	0.12196	58.40	2.887	1.420*
3	35.09	33.58	6.33	0.13583	78.33	1.828	1.327
4	48.25	35.17	6.58	0.15376	105.67	3.085†	1.220
5	56.42	35.99	12.56	0.16439	122.7	2.122	1.165
6	66.83	36.88	16.29	0.17747	144.6	2.204	1.101
7	75.88	37.56	21.56	0.18856	163.55	2.076	1.052
8	84.42	38.14	27.44	0.19884	181.53	1.960	1.009
9	91.45	38.56	34.99	0.20713	196.6	1.765	0.977
10	104.55	39.27	36.18	0.22236	224.9	2.147	0.922*
11	113.23	39.70	42.07	0.23233	244.41	2.121	0.891
12	122.57	40.12	47.31	0.24292	265.15	2.159	0.856
13	122.57	40.11	62.32	0.24290	265.2	1.640	0.858*
14	136.23	40.66	63.11	0.25821	295.6	1.935	0.812
15	167.89	40.70	90.41	0.29299	369.2	1.922	0.721*
16	191.43	42.33	126.24	0.31842	426.8	1.720	0.666
17	212.27	42.81	164.92	0.34070	478.14	1.563	0.621
18	240.98	43.38	195.64	0.37112	553.8	1.631	0.570*
19	95.37	35.15	49.48	0.20082	223.4	1.503	1.003*
20	97.42	37.96	44.62	0.21130	213.99	1.587	0.962
21	94.28	40.73	44.99	0.21647	194.4	1.365	0.943
22	99.34	44.12	36.54	0.23170	192.73	1.692	0.891
23	101.13	47.58	31.29	0.24387	184.6	1.870	0.853
24	104.03	50.00	25.97	0.25403	182.86	2.243	0.823
25	103.31	51.24	25.45	0.25703	177.7	2.192	0.814
26	105.64	53.13	21.23	0.26503	176.89	2.627	0.792*
27	107.14	56.60	22.26	0.27094	160.1	2.141	0.776
28	102.90	60.10	17.00	0.28320	155.44	2.696	0.745*
29	101.64	63.93	14.43	0.29343	145.9	2.879	0.720
30	97.12	68.26	14.62	0.30190	131.84	2.410	0.701*
31	96.51	72.52	10.97	0.31407	125.0	2.947	0.675

* Solving equations (4) and (9a) of Part III (*loc. cit.*) with a_{10}^- from Table I, these are calculated.

† These values have been plotted on $pK_1 \sqrt{\mu}$ curve in Fig. 2 of Part VIII (*loc. cit.*) of this work, where the points have been shown by $\square$ mark. The values of ' K_2 ' without asteriks, if similarly plotted, will also fall on the same straight line, but this has not been done to avoid clumsiness in the figure.

‡ These values were not considered while taking mean (*vide* : theoretical).

Table I shows the experimental p_H values and the corresponding values for the function :

$$a_A \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3 \text{ and } a_A^{-1} \cdot \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$$

(where A^- represents acetate ion and 'x', total concentration of "free acetic acid species" given by $c_{A^-} + C_A$). Fig. 1 represents equation (5b) (vide Part III, *loc. cit.*)

FIG. 1

(Ordinate magnified 10 times of the abs.)

graphically (c_{A^-} may be put equal to a_{A^-} in eq. 5b for solution of low ionic strengths). The slope and intercept on the ordinate of this straight line curve give the values of k_1 and k_2 , as 384×10^{-3} and 50×10^{-3} respectively. These are the average values of 'k₁' and 'k₂' over the range of ionic strengths employed. In Fig. 1 the circles represent the data from Table I for the first 18 solutions (No. 1 to 18) where ' C_A ' is constant and ' C ' varying, and the triangles represent those for the last 13 solutions (No. 19 to 31) in which ' C ' is constant and ' C_A ' varying. Table II, in which the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' have been calculated by following the procedure already described, is self-explanatory.

DISCUSSION

The only previous work on the subject appears to be that of Jana, Aditya and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 735) who from the E. M. F. measurements of the cells of the type,

conclude that the first stage dissociation of nickel acetate in aqueous solution is virtually complete, and the thermodynamic constant for the equilibrium (B) representing the second stage dissociation is given by $K_2 = 7.41 \times 10^{-3}$ at 30-32.5°. The method of calculation used by the authors in the above paper is open to the objection that the effect of the presence of acetic acid in the nickel acetate solution has not been taken into account in the calculation of the dissociation 'β' for NiAc⁺. Moreover, the authors by making an *ad hoc* assumption, that the first stage dissociation is complete, compute a value of ' K_2 ' and then using this value of ' K_2 ' they try to arrive at a value of 'α', the degree of dissociation for NiAc₂ into NiAc⁺ and Ac⁻. Since they find that 'α', thus obtained, is nearly 1, they conclude that the first step

dissociation is complete. This method is theoretically less sound than the present one which takes into account the effect of both dissociations simultaneously. However, from the magnitude of ' K_1 ' obtained in this paper and from the values of α_{NiAc} , (vide Table II), the present authors have no hesitation to assert that the first stage dissociation proceeds to a much larger extent than in the cases of other acetates studied in this series.

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